

The relationship between coping styles and posttraumatic growth and posttraumatic trauma level after Kahramanmaraş Earthquake

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Abstract

Earthquakes, like many other disasters, can cause loss of life, injuries, loss of home, loss of loved ones and unemployment. The prevalence rate of PTSD after natural disasters has been reported to be 10 to 15%. The aim of this study is to examine whether the level of post-earthquake trauma and post-traumatic growth and ways of coping with stress differ between individuals who directly and indirectly experienced the earthquake. In line with this purpose, the sample of the study consists of 33 people between the ages of 17-72 (Mean=38.0, SD=12.0) who were directly affected by the earthquakes with the epicentre of Kahramanmaraş on February 6, 2023 and 55 participants between the ages of 14-72 (Mean=39.0, SD=13.9) who did not experience an earthquake but were indirectly exposed to the effects of the earthquake through television and social media. Data were collected and analysed through Socio-Demographic Information Form, Posttraumatic Growth Inventory, Scale for Determining the Level of Post-Earthquake Trauma and Ways of Coping Scale. In our study, in accordance with the literature, it was determined that people who directly experienced the earthquake showed higher trauma levels than people who experienced it indirectly. Another finding in parallel with this is that helplessness scores were found to be higher in people who were directly exposed to the earthquake than those who were indirectly exposed to the earthquake. It is thought that the findings may provide useful information for practitioners to regulate the psychological effects of future earthquakes.

Keywords: Kahramanmaraş Earthquake; posttraumatic stress; posttraumatic growth; coping styles; indirect exposure; direct exposure

INTRODUCTION

Humans have faced many different disasters for centuries. Due to disasters as old as the history of humanity, millions of lives have been lost and cities and countries have been destroyed. Disasters are natural or human-induced events that cause physical damages, result in social and economic losses, interrupt or stop the ordinary life order. Türkiye has faced many disasters such as earthquakes, landslides, floods, avalanches, fires and especially earthquakes, due to its geographical structure, location, climate characteristics or socio-economic reasons (Özmen & Özden, 2013). Türkiye, located on the Alpine-Himalayan belt, one of the most active earthquake belts in the world, is in a position characterised as high risk in terms of earthquakes. INFORM Index scores define risk in five different categories as very low (0-1.9 points), low (2-3.4 points), medium (3.5-4.9 points), high (5-6.4 points) and very high (6.5-10 points). According to INFORM Risk Index's 2021 data, Türkiye is in the high risk category with 5 points. When the data on earthquake, which is one of the natural disasters, is analysed, the earthquake exposure score is 9.7 (KIZILAY, 2023).

As a matter of fact, when the earthquakes and their damages are analysed historically, it is seen that Türkiye has experienced very large earthquakes and faced devastating consequences. On 6 February 2023, two earthquakes of magnitude 7.7 and 7.6, with epicentres in Pazarcık and Elbistan, caused very severe damage and many loss of life. Due to these earthquakes, which affected an area of approximately 108.812 km² and 11 provinces, 50.783 people lost their lives and 156.353 people were injured (AFAD, 2023). The number of destroyed buildings was reported as 37.984 (AFAD, 2023). The effects of this earthquake, which affected a very large area and a large number of living beings, were felt in many fields, such as psychological, social and economic. The effects of earthquake on different living spaces, the level of these effect and other related factors are considered

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to be important for field applications and other studies to be carried out. In this direction, the study addresses the trauma levels of individuals who were directly and indirectly exposed to the earthquake, the growth levels after the traumatic event and the ways of coping with the stressful life event.

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Earthquakes, like many other disasters, can cause loss of life, injuries, loss of home and unemployment. Earthquakes have psychological effects as well as physical, social and economic effects. When the results of the studies in the literature are examined, it is seen that disasters are associated with negative outcomes such as alcohol use disorders, anxiety disorders, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder (Beaglehole et al., 2018; Bogstrand et al., 2016; Bonanno et al., 2010; Navarro-Mateu et al., 2017; Nolen-Hoeksema & Morrow, 1991; Smith et al., 1990). The prevalence rate of PTSD after natural disasters has been reported to be between 10 and 15% (Karancı, 2008). In a study conducted in 2017 with people exposed to the 7.0 magnitude Jiuzhaigou earthquake in China, it was reported that 46.3% of 1.114 participants showed PTSD symptoms (Qi et al., 2020). In another study conducted one month after the 2011 Van earthquake, PTSD symptom levels of university students were examined. In this study, it was reported that approximately 40% of the students had PTSD (Sönmez et al., 2017). In another study conducted with 384 individuals exposed to the 2020 Izmir earthquake, it was reported that 50.1% of the individuals showed mild, 21.4% moderate, 20.9% moderate-severe and 7.6% severe PTSD symptoms (Önder, 2022).

Post-traumatic stress symptoms can be seen not only in individuals who directly experience the traumatic event, but also in individuals who are indirectly exposed to the event through various media such as television and social media. This situation, which is described as the concept of secondary traumatic stress, is witnessing and learning the content of the traumatic life event to which other individuals are exposed, and thus, posttraumatic stress symptoms are observed in individuals who are indirectly exposed to the traumatic event (Figley, 1995). Various studies demonstrated that individuals who are exposed to many traumatic events such as terrorist attacks and natural disasters through the media have different levels of PTSD symptoms. Bernstein and colleagues (2007) conducted a one-year follow-up study after the 9/11 terrorist attacks in which the relationship between the follow-up of television news associated to the attacks and PTSD symptoms was evaluated. It was shown that as the duration of following television news about the attacks increased, the PTSD symptom level one year later increased and this relationship was statistically significant. The same study also revealed that decreased perceived social support was associated with increased PTSD symptoms (Bernstein et al., 2007). Another study on the 9/11 terrorist attacks illustrates that PTSD symptoms are associated with the follow-up of television news about the event in individuals who were directly exposed to the traumatic event, while this

relationship is not significant in individuals who were indirectly exposed to the traumatic event (Ahern et al., 2002). In the data of a representative New York sample obtained one month after Hurricane Sandy, posttraumatic stress symptom levels were compared between those who learnt about the hurricane only through traditional media such as television and those who learnt it through social media. It was observed that direct exposure to the event and learning it through social media demonstrated a significant relationship with PTSD symptom levels. It is stated that direct exposure to the event has a higher effect on PTSD symptom level (Goodwin et al., 2013). Sampath and colleagues (2018) conducted a study with students who experienced the aftershocks of the Nepal earthquake in 2015. The findings of the study showed that symptoms of acute stress disorder increased as the frequency of exposure to earthquake-related posts on television and the internet increased (Sampath et al., 2018). In another study conducted with children and their families who were indirectly exposed to the East Japan earthquake through television, it is seen that there is a significant relationship between the level of exposure to earthquake images and the level of psychological distress in both children and their families. It is revealed that the level of psychological distress increases as individuals are exposed to images related to the traumatic event through television (Ohnuma et al., 2023). In summary, these findings reveal the effect of indirect exposure to traumatic life event on PTSD symptoms. At the same time, the type of media exposure may also have different effects on PTSD symptoms.

Individuals show different reactions to traumatic life events. Not all individuals exposed to a traumatic life event display symptoms of mental disorders (Jin et al., 2014). Some individuals may also show positive changes in cognitive, emotional and behavioural areas known as posttraumatic growth (PTG) after traumatic events (Tedeschi & Calhoun, 2004). Individuals who show PTG after traumatic experiences may experience positive effects such as increasing the quality of close relationships and establishing close relationships, willingness to live, increased resilience and strength, exploration of new possibilities and redefining priorities in life (Lykins et al., 2007; Wu et al., 2016). It is thought that determining PTG levels in different life experiences and populations may have an important effect on determining the post-disaster needs of individuals and developing the interventions to be implemented.

As PTSD is not experienced following every traumatic life event, PTG is not experienced after every traumatic event, too. Studies have addressed the factors predicting PTG. Accordingly, the level of social support, income level, demographic characteristics such as age, education and gender, level of religiosity and the level of stress experienced after the traumatic life event are among the factors related to PTG (Armstrong et al., 2014; Henson et al., 2021; Hobfoll, 2002; Karancı & Erkam, 2007; Park & Fenster, 2004; Polantinsky & Esprey, 2000).

Another important factor predicting PTG is the coping style of individuals (Göral et al., 2006; Guo et al., 2017; Linley & Joseph, 2004; Martin et al., 2021; Mattson et al., 2018).

According to Lazarus (1991), coping is an evaluation process that supports individuals to manage the discrepancy between their resources and the demands arising from the situation. Lazarus and Folkman (1984) consider coping as a three-step evaluation process. Accordingly, individuals firstly evaluate whether the event or situation is a threat, then evaluate how to cope with this situation, what they can do, and lastly, the individual assesses new information and makes changes to previous evaluations if necessary. Psychological stress occurs if the person evaluates the coping resources as inadequate in the face of the threatening situation. Individuals cope with the problem in different ways. Folkman and Lazarus (1988) mentioned eight coping styles. These coping styles are distancing the individual from the problem, coping with confrontation, self-control, accepting responsibility, escape-avoidance, problem solving, seeking social support and positive reappraisal. In another study, Lazarus (1991) mentioned two types of coping styles as problem-focused and emotion-focused. While it is seen that problem-focused coping emphasises the change in the problematic situation, in emotion-focused coping style, the individual's effort to change the emotion created by the problem is seen rather than direct intervention to the problem.

Individuals who were in the disaster area and directly experienced the earthquake that occurred on 6 February 2023

and individuals who were not in the disaster area on that date but experienced the earthquake indirectly through the media are included in this study. Demographic characteristics of individuals, post-earthquake trauma levels, post-traumatic growth levels and ways of coping with stressful situations were examined. The aim of this study is to examine whether the level of post-earthquake trauma and post-traumatic growth and ways of coping with stress differ among individuals who directly and indirectly experienced the earthquake.

METHOD

Sample

The sample of the study consisted of 88 participants, 33 earthquake survivors between the ages of 17-72 (Mean=38.0, SD=12.0) who were directly affected by the earthquakes with the epicentre of Kahramanmaraş on February 6, 2023, and left the disaster area and settled in Aydın Nazilli Municipality student dormitory, and 55 participants between the ages of 14-72 (Mean=39.0, SD=13.9) residing in Aydın, who did not experience an earthquake but were indirectly exposed to the effects of the earthquake through television and social media. 70.5% of the 88 participants were female and 29.5% were male. The socio-demographic characteristics of the participants are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of participants in terms of socio-demographic characteristics

Variables		Directly Affected		Indirectly Affected		Total	
		n	%	n	%	N	%
Gender	Female	23	69.7	39	70.9	62	70.4
	Male	10	30.3	16	29.01	26	29.5
Age	14-35	13	40.6	22	40.0	35	39.7
	36-55	16	50	26	47.2	42	47.7
	56-75	3	9.3	7	12.7	10	11.3
Employment Status	Employed	16	48.5	24	43.6	40	45.4
	Unemployed	16	48.5	31	56.4	47	53.4
Education Status	Primary School	2	6.1	4	7.3	6	6.8
	Middle School	2	6.1	8	14.5	10	11.3
	High School	11	33.3	16	29.1	27	30.6
	Associate Degree	7	21.2	8	14.5	15	17.4
	Licence	9	27.2	14	25.5	23	26.1
Marital Status	Master's Degree	3	6.1	5	9.1	8	9.0
	Married	21	63.6	34	61.8	55	62.4
Income Level	Single	12	34.4	21	38.2	33	37.4
	Low	3	9.1	4	7.3	7	7.9
	Lower-Middle	4	12.1	10	18.2	14	15.9
	Middle	24	72.7	38	69.1	62	70.4
Living With	Upper	2	6.1	1	1.8	3	3.4
	Only Spouse	4	12.1	1	1.8	5	5.6
	Conjugal Family	16	48.5	11	20.0	27	30.6
	Extended Family	4	12.1	2	3.6	6	6.8
	Mother and/or Father	5	15.2	2	3.6	7	7.9
	Single	4	12.1	0	0	4	4.5
Age of the Building	Other	0	0	1	0.0	1	1.1
	0-10	18	58.1	5	16.1	23	26.1
	11-20	7	22.5	3	9.6	10	11.3
	21-30	3	9.6	3	9.6	6	6.8
	31-40	4	12.9	2	6.4	6	6.8
	41-50	2	6.4	1	3.2	3	3.4
	Over 50	0	0	1	3.2	1	1.1

House Building Style	Detached	5	15.2	2	3.6	7	7.9
	Family Apartment	3	9.1	7	12.7	10	11.3
	Condo	25	75.8	8	14.5	33	37.4
Place of Residence	Neighbourhood	10	30.3	6	10.9	16	18.1
	District Centre	16	48.5	10	18.2	26	29.5
	City Centre	7	21.2	1	1.8	8	9.0
Earthquake Precautions	Yes	6	18.2	0	0	6	6.8
	No	27	81.8	55	100	82	93.1
Experiencing an Earthquake Before	Yes	22	66.7	14	25.5	36	40.9
	No	11	33.3	3	5.5	14	15.9
Whose Responsibility is it to Take Precautions	Contractor	5	15.2	5	9.1	10	11.3
	Municipality	3	9.1	1	1.8	4	4.5
	State	24	72.7	11	20.0	35	39.7
	Society	1	3.0	1	1.8	2	2.2

Research design

In this study, a non-experimental comparative research design was used. Data regarding the variables subject to the research were collected from the participants who directly experienced the Kahramanmaraş earthquakes that took place on February 6 and were affected by the earthquake indirectly (TV, social media, etc.) and the collected data were analysed.

Data collection tools

Socio-Demographic Information Form: Socio-demographic information form includes questions prepared by the researchers to gather information about the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants. The form includes questions about the age, education level, socio-economic status, employment status, income level of the participants, as well as questions such as the age of the house they lived in before the earthquake, construction style, and the time of leaving the earthquake zone.

Posttraumatic Growth Inventory: This scale, developed by Tedeschi and Calhoun (1996), was adapted into Turkish by Kağan et al. (2012). The Turkish form of the scale consists of 21 items on a five-point Likert scale. The Turkish version of the scale, whose original form consists of a 5-factor structure, has a 3-factor structure: Change in self-perception, change in philosophy of life and change in relationships with others. High scores obtained from the scale express positive psychological change after the traumatic life event. In this Turkish adaptation study conducted with a sample of 723 people (Mean=20.19, SD=2.71), it was reported that the change in self-perception factor of the scale had a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.88, the change in philosophy of life factor had a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.78, the change in relationships with others factor had a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.77 and the whole scale had a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.92. The scale explains 64% of the total variance. As a result of the validity analyses, significant positive correlations ranging from .93 to .53 were reported among the factors of the scale. In summary, as a result of the reliability and validity analyses, it was reported that the Turkish form of the scale met the reliability and validity criteria.

Scale for Determining the Level of Post-Earthquake Trauma: This scale, developed by Tanhan and Kayri (2013),

was developed to determine the trauma levels of individuals who experienced an earthquake. In the scale development study conducted with 1505 participants between the ages of 15-86 who were affected by the 2012 Van earthquake, a scale consisting of 20 items and 5 factors (behavioural problems, excitement limitation, affective, cognitive structuring, sleep problems) was obtained. It was reported that the scale explained 54.29% of the total variance. It was reported that the behavioural problems factor of the scale had a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.64, the excitability factor 0.75, the affective factor 0.61, the cognitive structuring factor 0.68, the sleep problems factor 0.70 and the whole scale 0.87. Higher scores obtained from the scale indicate that the level of negative impact from the earthquake also increased. According to the results of the two-stage clustering analysis conducted in the study, it was reported that the 52.38 ± 5.05 point range taken from the scale reflects the threshold value where the earthquake victims are traumatised, and the scores above this range reflect the high trauma level, whereas the scores below this range reflect the low trauma level. In summary, it was reported that the scale developed as a result of reliability and validity analyses met the reliability and validity criteria.

Ways of Coping Scale: This scale, which was first developed by Folkman and Lazarus (1988) to determine which coping method individuals use in stressful situations, was developed by Karancı et al. (1999) in Turkish with 42 items and used to determine the coping methods of earthquake victims. In the study of Karancı et al., it was reported that the 42-item scale consisted of a 5-factor structure. It was reported that the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of the three-point Likert-type scale was 0.75 for problem-solving orientated coping, 0.78 for fatalistic approach, 0.69 for helplessness approach, 0.59 for seeking social support and 0.39 for avoidance. In summary, Karancı et al. (1999) reported that the 42-item Turkish form of the scale met the reliability and validity criteria. In this study, the short form of this scale adapted by Karancı et al. (1999) and the factor analysis results of Kesimci's (2003) study were used. Kesimci (2003) defined a 4-factor structure as fatalistic coping, social support-seeking coping, problem orientated coping and helplessness. Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the factors were reported as 0.73, 0.61, 0.73 and 0.66, respectively.

Operation

The data of the study were collected before the conference from the participants who attended the conference titled “*Ways to Reduce the Psychological Effects of Earthquake*”, given by Mehmet Şakiroğlu in the conference hall of the municipality building of Nazilli district of Aydın on the date of 01.04.2023. Participants who approved the Informed Consent Form stating that participating in and completing the study was voluntary were given a questionnaire form including Demographic Information Form, Posttraumatic Growth Inventory, Scale for Determining the Level of Post-Earthquake Trauma and Ways of Coping Scale, respectively. The questionnaire form was applied to the participants face to face.

RESULTS

According to the results of the analyses conducted to examine the distribution of the data related to the variables, it is seen that the kurtosis and skewness values of all variables are within the limits of -2 and +2. It is accepted that variables with kurtosis and skewness values within this limit meet the assumption of normal distribution (George & Mallery, 2010, pp. 126-134). Therefore, it can be said that the variables analysed in this study are normally distributed. The kurtosis and skewness values related to the distribution of the data are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: Kurtosis and skewness values for the distribution of data

Group	Scale	Kurtosis	Standard Error	Skewness	Standard Error
Directly Affected	Post-Traumatic Growth Inventory	0.05	0.79	0.64	0.40
	SDLPET*	-0.56	0.79	-0.48	0.40
	Fatalistic Coping	-0.30	0.79	0.17	0.40
	Social Support Search	-0.19	0.79	-0.38	0.40
	Problem Orientated Coping	0.94	0.79	-0.45	0.40
	Helplessness	-0.37	0.79	-0.01	0.40
Indirectly Affected	PTGI	0.31	0.63	-0.43	0.32
	SDLPET	-0.91	0.63	0.06	0.32
	Fatalistic Coping	-0.66	0.63	0.10	0.32
	Social Support Search	0.73	0.63	-0.62	0.32
	Problem Orientated Coping	-1.09	0.63	-0.22	0.32
	Helplessness	-0.37	0.63	0.23	0.32

* Scale for Determining the Level of Post-Earthquake Trauma

As a result of the analysis conducted to determine whether there is a difference between the individuals who were directly affected by the earthquakes with the epicentre of Kahramanmaraş on February 6 and the individuals who did not directly experience the earthquake but were indirectly affected by the earthquake in terms of the variables examined, it is seen that there is a statistically significant difference between the two groups in all other variables subject to examination, except for fatalistic coping and posttraumatic growth variables ($p < 0.05$). The post-earthquake trauma level and helplessness style coping style scores of individuals who directly experienced the earthquakes are statistically significantly higher than the post-earthquake trauma level and helplessness style coping style scores of individuals who were indirectly affected by the earthquake ($p < 0.05$). However, the mean scores of social support-seeking coping style and problem-focused coping style of individuals indirectly affected by the earthquake are statistically significantly higher than the mean scores of social support-seeking coping style and problem-focused coping style of individuals who directly experienced the

earthquake ($p < 0.05$). The results of intergroup analyses related to the variables examined are summarised in Table 3.

As a result of the group-specific correlation analysis conducted to determine the level of relationship between the variables subject to the research, it is seen that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between the post-traumatic growth variable and the fatalistic coping variable, between the post-traumatic growth variable and the social support seeking coping variable, between the post-earthquake trauma level variable and the helplessness style coping variable, and between the social support seeking coping variable and the problem orientated coping variable in both groups ($p < 0.05$). The dimension of the relationship between these variables, which are positively correlated in both groups, is higher in the group who directly experienced the earthquake. In the group of individuals who directly experienced the earthquakes, there was a moderate correlation between the posttraumatic growth variable and fatalistic coping variable ($r = 0.40$), a large

Table 3: Independent sample t-test table according to the scores of the variables before and after the intervention

Scale	n	Average	Standard Deviation	t	df	p
Post-Traumatic Growth Inventory	Directly affected	33	65.76	1.35	86	0.17
	Indirectly affected	55	60.73			

Table 3 continue

SDLPET*	Directly affected	33	68.15	16.75	2.74	86	>0.01
	Indirectly affected	55	57.80	17.36			
Fatalistic Coping	Directly affected	33	26.12	3.81	-0.42	86	0.67
	Indirectly affected	55	26.51	4.38			
Social Support Search	Directly affected	33	19.27	3.61	-2.62	86	0.01
	Indirectly affected	55	21.16	3.04			
Problem Orientated Coping	Directly affected	33	20.21	3.90	-2.36	86	0.02
	Indirectly affected	55	22.11	3.47			
Helplessness	Directly affected	33	13.30	2.03	2.83	86	>0.01
	Indirectly affected	55	11.91	2.34			

* Scale for Determining the Level of Post-Earthquake Trauma

correlation between the posttraumatic growth variable and social support seeking coping variable ($r=0.52$), a large correlation between the posttraumatic trauma level variable and helplessness style coping variable ($r=0.59$), fatalistic coping variable and social support-seeking coping variable in the large dimension ($r=0.72$), problem-focused coping variable in the large dimension ($r=0.63$) and finally social support-seeking coping variable and problem-focused coping variable in the large dimension ($r=0.76$). However, in the group of individuals indirectly affected by earthquakes, there was a small ($r=0.27$) and medium ($r=0.44$) correlation between the variable of post-traumatic growth and fatalistic coping, a small ($r=0.27$) and medium ($r=0.38$) correlation between the variable of fatalistic coping and social support-seeking coping,

a large ($r=0.38$) correlation between social support-seeking coping and problem-focused coping, a small ($r=0.27$), there is a statistically significant positive relationship between fatalistic coping variable and social support seeking coping variable in medium dimension ($r=0.38$), and between social support seeking coping and problem orientated coping in large dimension ($r=0.63$). Again, in the group of people who were indirectly affected by the earthquake, there is a statistically significant relationship between the variable of social support-seeking coping and helplessness-style coping in the medium dimension ($r=-0.30$), and between the variable of problem-focused coping and helplessness-style coping in the medium dimension ($r=-0.43$). The relationships between the variables are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: Correlation Analysis Table Regarding the Variables Analysed

Group	Scale	PTGI	SDLPET	Fatalistic Coping	Social Support Search	Problem Orientated Coping	Helplessness
Directly Affected	PTGI	-					
	SDLPET	0.25	-				
	Fatalistic Coping	0.40*	0.13	-			
	Social Support Search	0.52**	-0.02	0.72**	-		
	Problem Orientated Coping	0.32	-0.12	0.63**	0.76**	-	
	Helplessness	0.16	0.59**	0.29	-0.04	-0.09	-
Indirectly Affected	PTGI	-					
	SDLPET	0.13	-				
	Fatalistic Coping	0.27*	0.15	-			
	Social Support Search	0.44**	-0.16	0.38**	-		
	Problem Orientated Coping	0.23	-0.17	0.18	0.63**	-	
	Helplessness	-0.03	0.27*	0.01	-0.30*	-0.43**	-

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

In order to determine the relationship between coping styles and the level of post-earthquake trauma, regression analysis was conducted with the whole sample (n: 88) by controlling the variables of the participants' education level, the age of the house they lived in and the construction style of the house (the results of the analyses related to the controlled variables are summarised in Table 5) and the results showed that helplessness style coping style statistically significantly predicted the increase in the level of post-earthquake trauma ($p < 0.01$). There is a significant positive relationship between

these two variables ($r=0.57$) and helplessness coping style alone explains 33% of the variance of the trauma level experienced after the earthquake ($R^2=0.33$). Therefore, it can be said that one of the factors that increase the level of trauma experienced after the earthquake by individuals who were directly/indirectly affected by the earthquake is helplessness style coping. The results of the regression analysis between the level of post-earthquake trauma and helplessness style coping variables are summarised in Table 6.

Table 5: Table Regarding Variables Controlled in Regression Analyses

Regression Analysis Variables	Controlled Variables	Beta In	t	p	Partial Correlation	Tolerance
Post Traumatic Growth & Social Support Seeking Coping	Education Status	0.11	0.85	0.39	0.13	0.93
	Age of the House	-0.06	-0.44	0.65	-0.06	0.94
	Construction Style	-0.01	-0.11	0.90	-0.01	1.00
Post-Earthquake Trauma Level & Helplessness Style Coping	Education Status	-0.10	-0.86	0.39	-0.13	1.00
	Age of the House	0.02	0.21	0.82	0.03	0.88
	Construction Style	0.08	0.65	0.51	0.10	0.94

Table 6: Regression Analysis Table Regarding Post-Earthquake Trauma Level and Helplessness Style Coping Variables

Variable	B	Standard Error	Beta	t	p
Constant	17.28	10.92	-	1.58	0.12
Helplessness	3.95	0.85	0.57	4.64	>0.01

On the other hand, according to the results of the regression analysis conducted with the whole sample (n=88) by controlling the variables of the participants' educational status, age of the house they live in and the construction style of the house (the results of the analyses related to the controlled variables are summarised in Table 5) in order to determine the relationship between coping styles and posttraumatic growth, it is seen that the social support-seeking coping style predicts the increase in the level of posttraumatic growth to a statistically significant extent ($p < 0.01$). There is a significant positive

relationship between these two variables ($r=0.48$) and social support seeking coping style alone explains 24% of the variance of posttraumatic growth level ($R^2=0.24$). Therefore, it can be said that social support-seeking coping style is one of the factors that increase the level of posttraumatic growth after the earthquake for individuals who were indirectly or directly affected by the earthquake. The results of the regression analysis between posttraumatic growth and social support seeking coping variables are summarised in Table 7.

Table 7: Regression Analysis Table Regarding Posttraumatic Growth and Social Support Seeking Coping Variables

Variable	B	Standard Error	Beta	t	p
Constant	27.37	10.53	-	2.59	0.01
Social Support Seeking	1.92	0.52	0.48	3.68	>0.01

DISCUSSION

It is known that major earthquakes cause psychological as well as physical destruction (Massazza et al., 2019; Tang et al., 2018; Yazgan et al., 2006). Exposure to earthquake does not only mean experiencing the earthquake. While the people who are most exposed to the earthquake are undoubtedly the people who have experienced it, people who go to the earthquake area to help, people who have relatives in the earthquake zone and people who follow events through the media are also exposed to the earthquake. Depending on the level of exposure, the level of pathological findings also varies. In the studies, it was concluded that people who directly experienced traumatic events developed more pathological findings than people who were indirectly exposed to traumatic events (Goodwin et al., 2013). In people who are indirectly exposed to traumatic events through the media, it is known that following the event for a long time through the media increases trauma scores in parallel (Ahern et al., 2002; Sampath et al., 2018). In our study, in line with the literature, it was determined that people who directly experienced the earthquake showed higher trauma levels than people who experienced it indirectly. Another finding in parallel with this is that helplessness scores were found to be higher in people who were directly exposed to the earthquake than those who were indirectly exposed to the earthquake. The fact that the living conditions of the people who were directly

exposed to the earthquake changed completely, they had to leave the places where they lived, their daily routines changed and the losses they experienced explain the high helplessness scores. The fact that there is a positive relationship between helplessness and posttraumatic stress in the literature supports the findings of our study (Bolu et al., 2014; Sakarya & Güneş, 2013). One of the known methods to reduce the feeling of helplessness experienced by people experiencing helplessness is precautionary behaviour. It has been found in studies that helplessness scores decrease as they develop situation-specific and conscious precautionary behaviours (Erşan et al., 2021). Another way to reduce helplessness scores is psychotherapy. Studies show that the helplessness scores of people who undergo psychotherapy processes decrease (Özbağrıçık Çağlayan, 2014). Defining, making sense of and normalising the emotions experienced especially intensely in traumatic events helps to reduce helplessness scores in the psychotherapy process (Tetik et al., 2021). In addition, correctly understanding the cause of the traumatic events experienced during the psychotherapy process and re-inclusion of the person in the life process with normalisation after the event also helps to lessen helplessness scores.

When we look at the other important findings obtained from the study, the score differentiation in coping styles stands out. In particular, it was found that the problem-focused coping and

social support-seeking coping scores of the people who were directly exposed to the earthquake were lower than the people who were indirectly exposed to the earthquake. In this case, it may be effective that the problem-focused coping scores of the people who were directly exposed to the earthquake were lower due to the great losses they experienced, their continued uncertainty about the future, and their social support decreased as a result of having to change cities and the distance between them and the people they knew. In addition, the relationship between posttraumatic growth (development) scores and coping styles is also noteworthy. A positive relationship was found between posttraumatic growth (development) and fatalistic coping, social support-seeking coping, helplessness-style coping and problem-focused coping. The dimension of these relationships was higher in people who directly experienced the earthquake. These findings are consistent with the literature (Fariz et al., 2021; Kanat & Özpolat, 2016; Kardaş & Tanhan, 2018; Özlü et al., 2010). As a matter of fact, the stress experienced by the person in the traumatic process increases posttraumatic growth scores. In addition, the person's use of social support resources during the traumatic event increases posttraumatic growth scores (Dereboy et al., 2018). The fact that this relationship was stronger in those who directly experienced the earthquake suggests that the higher the level of trauma, the higher the posttraumatic growth will be.

Finally, one of the striking findings of the study was the scores obtained by the groups from the Scale for Determining the Level of Post-Earthquake Trauma. During the development of this scale, the average score was found to be 52 ± 5 . In our study, the trauma level score was found to be 68 in people who were directly exposed to the earthquake, while the trauma level score was found to be 57 in people who were indirectly exposed to the earthquake. This demonstrates that people who were indirectly exposed to the earthquake received an average score according to the scale. Based on this finding, it was thought that experiencing the earthquake directly may have traumatic effects at the level of PTSD, while those who experienced the earthquake indirectly would not show traumatic effects at the level of PTSD contrary to popular discourses. In other words, we can say that the trauma levels of people who were indirectly exposed to the traumatic event may increase, but this level does not lead to PTSD-level results.

Conclusion

This study contributes to the literature in various aspects. It can be said that making preparations for the earthquake before it may reduce the negative psychological reactions and trauma scores after the earthquake by reducing helplessness-type coping. On the other hand, for post-earthquake growth, it can be thought that arrangements that will motivate the search for social support and provide social support resources may be useful in the studies to be carried out after the earthquake. It provides information about who will be placed in tent cities and container cities to be established after the earthquake and what should be considered in this preference if there is a situation of moving to another city. This situation reveals the unique aspect of this study.

This study has some limitations. Firstly, since the data were obtained in a cross-sectional manner, the changes in trauma levels over the year cannot be monitored. In other words, it is incomplete to examine the changes in the relationships between the differences in the trauma levels of the people who experienced earthquake and the coping methods over time. In the future, it is thought that a longitudinal examination of the relationships between these variables will be useful both theoretically and in terms of developing intervention programmes.

As another limitation, it can be said that information was obtained only through self-report from people who had experienced an earthquake. It is thought that this situation may cause some biases and prejudices in the reactions of the participants. In future studies, in addition to the data obtained through self-report, it is thought that it would be more useful to conduct one-on-one interviews with people who have experienced an earthquake. As a final limitation, the fact that the data was collected before a conference regarding earthquake from participants who experienced the earthquake and moved to another city far from their homes may also have a confounding effect.

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Consent to participate: Informed consent was obtained from all the individual participants that were included in the study.

Data accessibility statement: Data will be available on request.

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